

Event metadata

Event title	Unlocking nf-core - customising workflows for your research
Event type	Workshop
Date of event	18 and 19 May 2023
Time of event	1:00 - 4pm AEST
Topic description	<p>Processing and analysing omics datasets poses many challenges to life scientists, particularly when we need to share our methods with other researchers and scale up our research. Public and reproducible bioinformatics workflows, like those developed by nf-core, are invaluable resources for the life science community.</p> <p>nf-core is a community-driven effort to provide high-quality bioinformatics workflows for common analyses including, RNAseq, mapping, variant calling, and single cell transcriptomics. A big advantage of using nf-core workflows is the ability to customise and optimise them for different computational environments, types and sizes of data and research goals.</p> <p>This workshop will set you up with the foundational knowledge required to run and customise nf-core workflows in a reproducible manner. On day 1 you will learn about the nf-core tools utility, and step through the code structure of nf-core workflows. Then on day 2, using the nf-core/rnaseq workflow as an example, you will explore the various ways to adjust the workflow parameters, customise processes, and configure the workflow for your computational environment.</p> <p>This workshop event and accompanying materials were developed by the Sydney Informatics Hub, University of Sydney in partnership with Seqera Labs, Pawsey Supercomputing Research Centre, and Australia's National Research Education Network (AARNet). The workshop was enabled through the Australian BioCommons - Bring Your Own Data Platforms project (Australian Research Data Commons and NCRIS via Bioplatforms Australia).</p>
Format description	<p>Workshop, online via Zoom over two three hour sessions as outlined in the schedule</p> <p>Georgie, Chis and Cali led the training by introducing key concepts and demonstrating the steps involved in the analysis. Participants were invited to code along and try out activities as outlined in the training materials.</p> <p>Questions were answered via Slack in real time.</p> <p>The workshop followed the tutorial linked in the 'Related work' section.</p> <p>A breakdown of timings and topics is provided in the schedule.</p>

	<p>Participation was free but subject to application with selection.</p> <p>Applications were reviewed by the organising committee.</p> <p>Number of participants = 37</p>
Identifier(s)/URL	https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/custom-nfcore
Licence	Materials are shared under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International agreement unless otherwise stated on the materials
Keywords	<p>Bioinformatics http://edamontology.org/topic_0091</p> <p>Analysis http://edamontology.org/operation_2945</p> <p>Workflows http://edamontology.org/topic_0769</p> <p>Nextflow</p> <p>nf-core</p>
Contact	training@biocommons.org.au
Audience	This workshop is for researchers and bioinformaticians who are already (or soon will) be using and customising nf-core workflows.
Prerequisites	<p>The workshop will be conducted in a Unix environment. Command line experience is required. Prior experience running Nextflow and nf-core workflows is recommended.</p> <p>You must be associated with an Australian organisation for your application to be considered.</p>
Technical requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slack was used to facilitate discussions. • Access to the internet, speakers, a webcam, microphone and Zoom. • Participants were provided with access to virtual machines running on Pawsey Nimbus infrastructure. Packages, workflows and data were preinstalled as described here: https://sydney-informatics-hub.github.io/customising-nfcore-workshop/setup.html
Learning outcomes	<p>By the end of the workshop you should be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recognise how Nextflow and nf-core enable reproducible and portable bioinformatics • Write and run a basic nf-core run command • Describe nf-core code/directory structure (config, modules, submodules, workflow, main.nf) • Adjust the run command to customise the workflow • Describe Nextflow configuration hierarchy • Create and use a params file to customise workflow parameters • Create and use a custom config file to adjust resource usage • Apply external arguments not available as a workflow parameter to a process

Lead Trainers	<p>Dr Georgina Samaha, Sydney Informatics Hub, University of Sydney</p> <p>Dr Cali Willet, Sydney Informatics Hub, University of Sydney</p> <p>Dr Chris Hakkaart, Seqera Labs.</p>
Facilitators	<p>Dr Sarah Beecroft, Pawsey Supercomputing Research Centre</p>
Infrastructure and software provision	<p>Audrey Stott, Pawsey Supercomputing Research Centre</p> <p>Alex Ip, AARNet</p> <p>Steele Cooke, AARNet</p>
Related work	<p>This workshop follows the accompanying training materials that were developed by the Sydney Informatics Hub, University of Sydney in partnership with Seqera Labs, Pawsey Supercomputing Research Centre, and Australia's National Research Education Network (AARNet).</p> <p>https://sydney-informatics-hub.github.io/customising-nfcore-workshop/</p>